

ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF CONGENITAL CLUBFOOT

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Abstract

Congenital clubfoot is one of the most common congenital malformations, affecting 1-3 per 1000 live births and occurring twice as often in male fetuses. Although it is called congenital, it is not an embryonic malformation but is a developmental deformity that occurs in the second trimester of pregnancy.

Keywords: clubfoot, pathogenesis, CTEV

To date, the exact etiology of the malformation is not known and there are several possible etiopathogenic theories:

Mechanical theory (Ombredanne) - is one of the oldest theories developed on the aetiology of clubfoot; - mechanical factors incriminated pathogenetically are: fetomaternal dystocia; oligohydramnios; uterine malformations (bicornuate uterus, infantile uterus); twinning; fetal trauma; amniotic flange [1,2].

Vascular theory - decreased blood flow in the anterior tibial artery and its derivatives [1].

Genetic theory - is supported by hereditary transmission demonstrated in 10-15% of cases. So far no karyotypic chromosomal abnormalities have been detected. It is assumed that the malformation results from genetic mutations caused by teratogenic factors.

Developmental arrest theory (Max Böhm) - the foot passes during embryonic development through 4 intermediate stages; in the third month the foot is in equinus → follows a position of abduction and supination → then supination disappears → subsequently returns to the normal position.

Developmental arrest in one of these stages causes congenital clubfoot.

Neuro-motor plate theory (P. Lombard) - considers the clubfoot position to be secondary to an imbalance of postural tone of agonist and antagonist muscles through a defective mechanism of synaptic transmission between the cerebrospinal extrapyramidal system and peripheral motor neurons. Restoration of neuromuscular balance is achieved within 6 to 24 months [1].

Genetic component in the aetiopathogenesis of congenital clubfoot

CTEV is a multifactorial disorder, therefore, the combination of genetic and environmental factors are known contributors to this developmental abnormality. To date, a number of genes involved in limb patterning, such as PITX1, HOXA, HOXD, TBX4 and RBM10, as well as genes involved in muscle contraction, have been identified as possible factors. Of the many environmental factors investigated, maternal smoking appears to

hold the strongest consistent association with this disorder [4].

Genes in the Homeobox family

Homeobox genes (HOXA, HOXD) are a family of transcription factors that play a central role in the morphogenesis processes of embryonic development. In particular, this family determines the correct genesis of the axial skeleton and limbs, which is why they have been proposed as candidate genes for CTEV pathogenesis [4, 3].

Caspases pathway genes

Aspartate-dependent cysteine proteases (caspases) are part of a family of cysteine proteases that play a key role in the processes of apoptosis, necrosis and inflammation. This pathway has been investigated because caspase activity appears to be linked to proper limb development [4].

Collagen family genes

Collagen family genes have also been linked to CTEV. Related genetic research has focused on the COL9A1 and COL1A1 genes. COL9A1 codes for one of the three alpha chains of type IX collagen, a component of hyaline cartilage, while COL1A1 codes for the pro-alpha 1 chains of type I collagen, a component of most connective tissue found abundantly in bones and tendons [4].

T-box family

The T-box family comprises transcription factors that play a crucial role in embryogenesis and morphogenesis. Like other genes with a similar role, they are possible genetic inducers of CTEV [4].

PITX1-TBX4 pathway

The TBX4 protein is a transcription factor that is mainly expressed in the hind limb and is thus associated with CTEV pathogenesis. It has been studied in association with another transcription factor, PITX1, which is part of the same pathway. The PITX1-TBX4 pathway is responsible for early limb development. Numerous studies report that mutations in genes encoding the transcription factors PITX1 and TBX4 lead to reduced lower limb musculature and classic clubfoot phenotypes [4].

Environmental causes in utero

Smoking during pregnancy has been associated with congenital malformations, including clubfoot [46]. NAT1 and NAT2 N-acetylation genes modulate biotransformation of exogenous substances such as tobacco smoke, and one study found that there were significantly more NAT2 slow acetylators among cases of clubfoot.

References

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